

Constituency and Constituency Test

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Abstract

The article discusses the structures of syntax, which is one of the most basic levels of linguistics. Identifying the syntactic constituency is the most critical part of syntactic structures, and those depend on the constituency. With the basic knowledge of the constituency test, it is possible to acquire fundamental skills in syntax and linguistics. The researcher, therefore, tries to describe and analyse the constituency, tests, and topic-related syntactic structures.

Introduction

This short article aims to define the syntactic constituency, show some examples, and identify among them. In addition, the researcher discusses the definition and visualize them in the following paragraphs.

Firstly, single words are constituents, but frequently we can see some exceptions like specific contractions and certain possessives. For example, Ritu is coming here!

Secondly, complete sentences are constituents, for instance, Come here!

Also, any sequence of words which a single word can functionally replace must be a constituent. For example,

'The girl with black hair stood first in the class.' 'She stood it.'

Then, any sequence of words can stand alone to answer a question. For instance,

Who stole the money? The man.

Moreover, any series of words conjoined to an independently identifiable constituent is a constituent. i.e., Tuli helped the boy in the green hat and Rasel.

Finally, any series of words which can be stated as a unit and still generate a grammatical sentence with a similar meaning is a constituent—such as Rima worked on the ancient text with great care. With great care, she worked on the ancient text.

Discussion

In the discussion part, the researcher presents how to test the syntactic constituency. He will find the idea that sentences are hierarchically organized into constituent structures. He represents these constituent structures in trees and underlined diagrams. He also builds a set of rules to generate those structures, and finally, he looks at constituency tests that can be used to test the structures. Parts of speech are the labelling system for constituent structure. Finally, in the following subsequent paragraphs, the researcher will discuss with examples and show tree diagrams.

Firstly, by giving an example, he will start his discussion.

a) The students loved their syntax assignments.

On a purely intuitive level, certain words are more closely related. For example, the word *the* is tied more to students meaning than to *love* or *syntax*. A related intuition can be seen by looking at the sentences below:

b) The students loved their phonology readings.

c) The students hated their morphology professor.

Compare these sentences to the ones in (b) and (c). We will immediately see the relationship between *the students* and *their syntax assignments* and *the students* in the first sentence and *their phonology readings* in (a) is the same. Similarly, the relation between *the students* and *their morphology professor* in (c), while of a different kind (hating instead of loving), is of a similar type: There is one group (*the students*) who are either hating or loving another entity (*their syntax assignments* or *their morphology professor*).

In order to capture these intuitions (the intuition that certain words are more closely connected than others and the intuition about relationships between words in the sentence), we need a more complex notion. The notions we use to capture these intuitions are **constituency** and **hierarchical structure**. The notion that '*the*' and '*students*' are closely related is captured by the fact that we treat them as part of a bigger unit that contains them, but not other words. We have two different ways to represent this bigger unit. One of them is to put underlines around units:

d) the students

The other is to represent the units with a group of lines called a tree structure:

These bigger units are called constituents (Carnie, 2006).

The researcher tries to define the constituent in the paragraph. A string of words functioning together as a unit is called a constituent. In other words, a group of expressions within a more extensive phrase that forms a unit is known as a constituent. For example,

f) The lazy dog was sleeping under the desk.

Moreover, the constituency is syntactic theory's most critical and fundamental notion. Constituents capture the intuitions mentioned above. The "relatedness" is captured by membership in a constituent. As we will see, it also allows us to capture the relationships between constituents alluded to in (c) and (d).

Also, constituents do not float out in space. Instead, they are embedded inside one another to form larger and larger constituents. It is a hierarchical structure. For shadowing the discussion below a bit, here is the structure we can develop for a sentence like this:

Hypothesis

When we study that 'Syntax as a science,' we learn that linguistics in general (and syntax specifically) is up to the criterion of the scientific method. That is why; if we make a hypothesis about something, we must be able to test that hypothesis. We have proposed the hypothesis that sentences are composed of higher-level constituents. Constituents are represented in tree structures and are generated by rules. If the hypothesis of the constituency is correct, we should be able to test it in general and the specific instances of the rules.

Furthermore, it is helpful to reconsider the specifics of the hypothesis to determine what kinds of tests are needed. The definition of constituents as a unit. If this is the case, we should find instances where groups of words behave as single units. These instances can serve as tests for the hypothesis. In other words, they are *tests for the constituency*. There are many constituency tests listed in the syntactic literature. Therefore, the researcher examines only five constituency tests: answering questions, cliffing, coordination, substitution, and deletion.

Firstly, we can identify the constituency by answering to question. We may ask as many questions as possible related to the target sentence. The answers will help to find the constituency. For example,

- g) The boy stole the bag.
 Who stole the bag?
 'The boy.'

What did the boy do? 'Stole the bag.' What did he steal? 'The bag.'

Movement is our second test of the constituency. If we move a group of words around in the sentence, then they (words) are a constituent because we can move them as a unit. Some typical examples are shown in (h), (i), and (j). *Cliffing* (h) involves putting a string of words between *It was* (or *It is*) and a *that* at the beginning of the sentence. *Preposing* (i) (*pseudo cliffing*) involves putting the string of words before a *is/are what* or *is/are who* at the front of the sentence. *Passive* forms are shown in (j). Briefly, it involves putting the object in the

subject position, the subject in a "by the phrase" (after the word *by*), and changing the verb form (for example, from *kiss* to *was kissed*).

h) *Cliffing*:

The dog was sleeping under the desk.

It was under the desk that the dog was sleeping.

It was the dog that was sleeping under the desk.

*It was *under the* that the dog was sleeping.

h) *Preposing*:

Big bowls of beans are what

he likes.

(*He likes big bowls of beans.*)

j) *Passive*:

The big boy was kissed by [the slobbering dog].

(from *The slobbering dog kissed the big boy.*)

Again, the movement test is only reliable when someone keeps the meaning roughly the same as the original sentence.

Coordination is our third constituency test. This test is when a coordinating conjunction joins the strings of the words "and" and they act like a single unit. This unit also works as an argument.

k) Roni and the boy went to the store.

l) *Roni and very blue went to the store.

If we can coordinate a group of words with a similar group of words, they (words) form a constituent.

Moreover, the minor constituent is a single word, so if someone can substitute a group of words with a single word, we know that a group forms a constituent. For example, consider the italicized NP in (m) and (n); it can be replaced with a single word (in this case, a pronoun). It is the *substitution test*. For example,

m) *The man from Dhaka* flew only ultra-light planes.

n) *He* flew only ultra-light planes.

There is one crucial caveat to the test of substitution: There are many cases in our rules of optional items, those things marked in parentheses like the AP in (NP (D) (AP) NP). When we replace a string of words with a single word, how do we know we are not just leaving off the optional items? We must keep the meaning closely related to the original to avoid this problem. It requires some judgment on our part. Unfortunately, none of these tests are absolutes.

The final test we will use is the '*deletion.*' By this test, some parts of the sentences can be deleted. The remaining part is grammatical. For example,

o) We went there to buy snacks. We went there.

* We went buy snacks

Conclusion

In conclusion, we look at the idea that sentences are hierarchically organized into constituent structures. We represent these constituent structures in trees and underlined diagrams. We also develop a set of rules to generate those structures, and finally, we look at constituency tests that can be used to test the structures. Finally, parts of speech are the labelling system for constituent structure.

References

- Carnie, A. (2013). *Syntax A Generative Introduction* (Third Edition), The University of Arizona. Retrieved from:
https://ia803005.us.archive.org/10/items/AndrewCarnieSyntaxAGenerativeIntroductionWileyBlackwell2012/Andrew%20Carnie%20-%20Syntax_%20A%20Generative%20Introduction-Wiley-Blackwell%20%282012%29.pdf. Accessing date: 15.04.2023
- Sportiche, D. (1988). A Theory of Floating Quantifiers and Its Corollaries for Constituent Structure. *Linguistic Inquiry*, 19(3), 425–449. Retrieved from:
<https://www.jstor.org/stable/25164903>
- Uriagereka, J. (1998). *Rhyme and Reason: An Introduction to Minimalist Syntax*. Cambridge Mass: MIT Press. ISBN: 9780262210140720, October 1998. Retrieved from:
<https://mitpress.mit.edu/books/rhyme-and-reason>
- Williams, E. (1994). *Thematic Structure in Syntax*. Cambridge: The MIT Press, p. 266.